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FAIR Data Guidelines**

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Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to promote the adoption of FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) in the European nanoscience community, particularly for small and medium-sized research infrastructures (RI). It draws on the experiences of the ExPaNDS and PaNOSC projects to provide practical and accessible recommendations.

The following topics are addressed:

- Providing recommendations for adapting facilities’ policies and practices to facilitate the publication and use of FAIR data
- Developing a common metadata framework to support FAIR data within the nanoscience community
- Developing an approach to harmonize facilities’ data management plans (DMP)
- Promoting best practices in Persistent Identifier Infrastructure (PID)

1. Introduction

Providing reliable services for research data management (RDM) is critical for sustainable research. In 2016, the FORCE 11 group (<https://www.force11.org>) introduced a new set of principles for these types of RDM services: to be FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable – where the term FAIR was launched at a Lorentz workshop in 2014 (<https://www.lorentzcenter.nl/lc/web/2014/602/info.php3?wsid=602>).

Specifically, this means that research data should be:

- *Findable*: Data and metadata should be easy to locate, both by humans and machines. Basic machine-readable descriptive metadata enables the discovery of datasets and services.
- *Available (or Accessible)*: Data and metadata should be archived long-term and made available in such a way that they can be easily retrieved by humans and machines or be used locally through standard communication protocols.
- *Interoperable*: Data should be available in a format that can be exchanged, interpreted, and combined in a (semi-)automated manner with other data, to be carried out by human and machine operations.
- *Reusable*: A good description of data and metadata ensures that the data can be re-used for future research and are comparable. It must be possible to properly cite the data, and the conditions under which the data can be re-used should be presented in a way that is easy to understand for humans and machines.

The aim of this document is to provide FAIR data recommendations for Junior Scientists involved in the RIANA project and for the nano technology community at large.

In *section 2*, we present prior achievements mainly from previous joint work in the Photon and Neutron (PaN) community, exemplarily focusing on the PanOSC (<https://www.panosc.eu/>) and ExPaNDS (<https://expands.eu/>) projects.

In *section 3*, we show how best-practice experience can be transferred from large infrastructures to small/medium size RIs.

In *section 4*, we conclude our report with a summary of main recommendations and an outlook for how the work may be continued further during the completion of RIANA project.

2. FAIR data standards in large RIs

The photon and neutron communities encompass over 40 000 scientists who utilise the various European synchrotrons, free electron lasers, and neutron sources for diverse scientific areas. These disciplines span a broad range, from protein research, virology, and biomedicine to technical fields such as battery development, transportation, and chip research, as well as studies in cultural heritage.

Historically, the interaction between the above-mentioned disciplines has been limited, and the primary focus of large infrastructures is the efficient use of their facilities. Therefore, long-term policies to handle the valuable data collected during beamtimes were not consistently defined and often relied on undocumented agreements between the principal investigator and the facility. Generally, there was little emphasis placed on long-term archiving, proper annotation of data with metadata, or reuse of data.

During the last years, the PaN communities launched many collaborations to streamline the workflows of such resource-intensive infrastructures by ensuring that data is FAIR. In alignment with the objectives of the call HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01, RIANA contributes to the EOSC by offering PaN-related data, services, and training resources to bolster the FAIRness of PaN data.

This helped the facilities implementing the following actions:

- Providing templates and best practices for data policies and FAIR data management, aligning with the EOSC and empowering facilities to continuously self-assess their FAIRness in implementing these regulations
- Supplying reference datasets and their corresponding cloud-ready analysis pipelines for a wide range of techniques, serving as exemplary models for future activities
- Enhancing the findability of scientific photon and neutron data in the EOSC by contributing to widely used metadata systems, enabling their content to be harvested through standard protocols
- Developing ontologies for experimental techniques and providing appropriate keywords for the Nexus file format
- Making training platforms available in the EOSC marketplace
- Engaging high-level management from facilities and national stakeholders in the project's outcomes primarily by showcasing interviews

More particularly, the EU project ExPaNDS explored how FAIR data can be enabled within PaN facilities, working closely with its sister project PanOSC. ExPaNDS provides a framework of guidelines that facilities can use to ensure that data arising from experiments is FAIR and suitable for sharing and reuse, and that the data are easier to be used by the experimenters themselves.

2.1 FAIR Components

The components of the framework are illustrated in Figure 1 and described below.

Figure 1: Components of FAIR data

FAIR Policy

PaN facilities issue data policies describing the facility’s approach to the management and publication of experimental data, and the rights and obligations of users. The ExPaNDS framework considers how policies should be expressed so that the experimental data in scope should be *FAIR when it leaves the facility* [1,3]. This gives a commitment to the facility to uphold the FAIR principles. This is further expanded into a set of 21 policy principles for the facility to consider when drawing up its data policy.

FAIR Guidelines

Experiments within facilities are highly diverse in terms of instruments and techniques used, science discipline, and in the volume and nature of data collected; this makes it difficult to come up with a unique set of comprehensive FAIR data guidelines. However, many facilities offering RI access to external users follow a conceptually comparable process of users submitting proposals, performing experiments during a visit, and analysing and publishing results as illustrated in Figure 2.

Each stage of the process is supported by IT systems with the opportunity to collect metadata. The ExPaNDS guidelines [2,7] recommend mandatory and desirable metadata that should be collected at each stage to ensure a FAIR description of the experimental data, as illustrated in Figure 3.

The guidelines describe mappings to standards, such as the DataCite schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>), and how these mappings can be used for aggregators like B2Find (<https://b2find.eudat.eu/>), which enhances data findability.

Further, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are a key aspect of FAIR data, and the framework includes recommendations on their use for data [5], but also emerging standards for resources including instruments and samples that are of value to the PaN community.

Figure 2: General process of access to research infrastructures for external users

Figure 3: Experimental process and metadata within information systems

FAIR Tools

FAIR data practices need to be embedded in software tools. Facilities have developed common approaches to data cataloguing in the ICAT (<https://icatproject.org/>) and SciCAT toolkits (<https://scicatproject.github.io/>) used in several European facilities.

ExPaNDS extends these approaches to support data federation via a common search API (Application Programming Interface) and OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) interface, conforming to FAIR framework recommendations [10]. Additionally, new shared vocabularies were identified to support FAIR data, including PaN Experimental Techniques (PaNET), an ontology of analytic techniques supported by facilities [9]. However, techniques are very diverse, and additional information is needed to fully describe data to make it FAIR.

FAIR Experiments

For a particular experiment we need the details of the environment and instrument taking the measurements, the data produced, and the post-processing undertaken; this information needs to be supplied by the experimental team. The ExPaNDS framework advocates Data Management Plans (DMPs) to identify additional attributes to make data FAIR. This can be burdensome: the DMP questionnaire proposed by PaNOSC identified 115 questions to give a complete picture of experimental data [11]. In practice, many of these depend on the instrument and computing infrastructure, and standardised responses can be supplied, drastically reducing the user input. The ExPaNDS framework discusses this within guidelines on the implementation and use of DMPs [4,8]. The recommendations¹ issued from ExPaNDS/PaNOSC projects are summarised in the following section 2.2.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/6821676>

2.2 Recommendations

Formal Policy

A data policy framework has been set up within the ExPaNDS project to provide guidance to the development of data policies that are compatible across facilities. The purpose of the framework is twofold:

1. To promote a common coverage and approach to data policy so that the policies of ExPaNDS RIs have a consistent scope, allowing users to compare policies and enable cross-facilities working and data sharing.
2. To recommend the evolution of RIs' data policies to enable the production and publication of FAIR data.

Across nine themes, the ExPaNDS data policy framework discusses key principles that should be considered in relation to RIs' data policy making. The nine themes are:

1. General drivers and principles
2. Roles and responsibilities
3. Scope
4. Enabling FAIR data
5. Necessary restrictions to data sharing
6. Availability of infrastructure and responsibility for costs
7. Data management planning requirements
8. Recognition and reward for data usage
9. Reporting requirements, compliance monitoring, and any possible sanctions

Out of this discussion, 21 policy elements have emerged to create the framework. The elements are those in which RIs need to make choices on the level of commitments which they are prepared to make as well as the obligations that they require of users as presented in the following.

Use of the FAIR Metadata Framework

- Using the FAIR metadata framework as a basis, carefully design the metadata acquisition plan for a particular instrument through dialogue between the different stakeholders (instrument scientists, users, data acquisition and management staff). Metadata records heavily depend on users (e.g. calibration, sample, experimental notes) should be given special attention.
- Implement a robust sample metadata database system (as a unique source) integrated in the other data management resources of the facility.
- Implement and promote the use of electronic logbooks / notebooks. A system of information tagging would facilitate the parsing of the different types of metadata mentioned by machines.
- Favour the use of persistent identifiers for data, people, instruments and samples when possible.
- Agree on and control the visibility level of each metadata record, in agreement with the embargo period duration.

Research Metadata Lifecycle

- Across the experimental lifecycle within PaN RIs, there are multiple information sources – both human and machine – that play a role in metadata production and collection. In many cases, it is important that these sources interact and integrate within and across the various stages of the experimental lifecycle.
- Each step in the experimental lifecycle produces specific metadata.
- Metadata will be stored in files and exposed in the Metadata catalogue. Exposition and storage should ideally be made using their appropriate metadata schemata.
- Avoid dependency on a particular data format when aggregating (meta)data in files and data catalogue. One metadata standard or file format might not be enough to express the information to be stored and exposed.

Alignment of the MetaData Framework with Other Data Cataloguing, Indexing and Discovery Services

- Having a common search API offers the possibility to query a series of fields that can be directly mapped to the metadata framework. However, not all fields can be queried yet and the framework can thus serve as a basis to extend the number of fields searchable by the API.
- EOSC indexing and discovery services such as B2FIND and OpenAIRE offer the means to make PaN datasets more findable by those outside the PaN domain. To enable these generic tools to harvest metadata, it is important that PaN RIs provide: 1.) OAI-PMH endpoints; and 2.) mappings of metadata to the metadata schemas used by the EOSC services.
- Regarding metadata mapping, it is important to bear in mind the purpose of services such as B2FIND and OpenAIRE. Such tools are aimed at cross-domain discovery; they are not designed to capture the full domain-specific richness that is possible using the ExPaNDS metadata framework.
- It is not necessary, nor should we expect to map every aspect of the framework to the metadata schemas of the cross-domain EOSC services. However, to meet the primary purpose of the EOSC discovery tools, it is important that the information we make available through B2FIND and OpenAIRE is: 1.) sufficient for the initial enquiries of a non-domain specialist; and 2.) able to point that user to where they can find further details.
- Given the nature of the B2FIND and OpenAIRE metadata schemas, it is not possible to map every metadata type found in the more extensive ExPaNDS metadata framework to these schemas. Additionally, multiple ExPaNDS metadata types may map to a given element/property in the B2FIND and OpenAIRE metadata schemas, meaning a one-to-one mapping is not always possible.
- As an example, the framework provides some initial guidelines on how ExPaNDS metadata types for a raw dataset could be mapped to the metadata schema of B2FIND. Several key recommendations emerge from this example mapping exercise:
 - To achieve as much richness in the metadata mapping as possible, the recommendation is that PaN providers should seek to map not only mandatory elements but also recommended and optional metadata elements.

- To increase interoperability and consistency, controlled vocabulary should be used wherever possible, especially for metadata types such as keyword and discipline.
- The use of PIDs and the related identifier metadata type offers the opportunity to improve findability and to link to other resources, perhaps including sample and instrument PID, if these were to be adopted widely by the PaN community in future.
- The description metadata type should not be overlooked for its potential to provide valuable additional information, including about the methods and sample.
- The process of mapping the ExPaNDS framework to the B2FIND schema suggests that some potentially important metadata types may be missing from the ExPaNDS framework. As such, the PaN community may wish to add to and improve upon the current version of the ExPaNDS metadata framework, where experience and practice indicate this could be beneficial.
- At present, each PaN provider interacts with B2FIND and OpenAIRE on an individual basis. The result is that different metadata mappings are produced by the different facilities. While over time, we might expect the adoption of ExPaNDS metadata framework to lead to more consistency in these mappings, it is likely that local practices and policies will still result in some ongoing differences.

Standard Data Format (Nexus)

- Recommendation is to use the NeXus/HDF5 data format as a self-contained and self-descriptive format to store data and scientific metadata, facilitating data exchange and reuse.
- Administrative metadata can to a certain extent also be stored using NeXus.
- The usage of Nexus application definitions is advocated.

Research Software

- Refer to the FAIR principles for Research software whenever having to cite software.
- According to the Software Citation Principles², several quality criteria must be fulfilled whenever citing software:
 - Credit and attribution
 - Unique identification
 - Persistence
 - Accessibility

² Smith A., Katz D., Niemeyer K., FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. (2016) Software Citation Principles. PeerJ Computer Science 2:e86. <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-86/>

3. Fair data for small/medium RIs

Small and Medium RIs face the challenge of implementing FAIR data policies, often without the necessary critical mass to develop a comprehensive and ambitious approach. In the RIANA project, where large and small/medium RIs collaborate, it has been considered essential to include specific recommendations tailored for the latter.

The minimal elements that a FAIR data system at an RI should include are recommended as follows:

- A simplified formal policy, explicitly outlining a gradual implementation on a best-effort basis.
- Data and metadata standards applied stepwise for different instruments and techniques.
- Basic local storage following practical local rules.
- The use of external repositories for open data implementation after an embargo period, relying on standard search options by external repositories instead of a proprietary data catalogue.

As an example, we describe a pilot project jointly developed by Universidad Autónoma de Madrid and Universidad de Sevilla to implement FAIR data practices in their respective ion beam facilities, both involved in RIANA (CMAM and CNA).

The project began by identifying one beamline/technique at each RI to serve as a pilot implementation, aiming to create a foundation that can be extended to other instruments in the future. At CNA, the selected technique was RBS, while at CMAM, it was TOF-ERDA. In both cases, the data files have simple and reproducible structures, making the primary challenges related to metadata and the workflow of the entire process.

A draft formal data policy was developed (see Annex) as a first element of FAIR data implementation, ensuring a common framework for both institutions. The intention is to handle data in a federated manner, and the policy will be made public via the proposal application webpage (shared by both facilities) once the project implementation is complete.

As a second element, a metadata structure was designed in collaboration with instrument scientists at both RIs, leading to the creation of a common framework. This structure consists of:

- A shared section that imports experiment proposal data from the proposals database using the proposal ID code.
- A technique-specific section containing fields relevant to each technique. Some parameters, such as certain accelerator settings, are common across techniques, while others are technique-specific and must be manually input by users via a dedicated user interface developed within the project.

To define the metadata, the following information is required:

- Parameter name
- Example value and units
- Parameter definition
- Required or optional status

- Associated instrument

The metadata format is JSON, chosen for its human and machine readability, facilitating interoperability and automation in data processing.

The user interface allows users to enter metadata values through a graphical interface. Several buttons facilitate data handling within the system:

- *“Save General Info”*, *“Save Experiment Setup”*, and *“Save Detection System”*: These buttons store the entered values in memory before generating the JSON file.
- *“Save JSON”*: Generates the final JSON metadata file.
- *“Clean JSON”*: Clears the stored values in memory.
- *“Load JSON”*: Loads values from a previously generated JSON file.

For this implementation, we have used the React framework for the front-end, developed in JavaScript, HTML, and CSS, along with Electron to generate the executable for the desktop application. Additionally, a back-end is being implemented using Node.js, which will connect to the proposal database and retrieve experiment data automatically through an internal code reference. This will streamline the metadata input process and reduce manual entry errors.

With the metadata structure and interface now developed, testing will begin in real experiments over the coming months.

Once data and metadata are generated, the next step in the workflow is to develop a simple script that reads both inputs and creates a final dataset in a format compatible with public repository uploads. When this system is in place, data files will be systematically uploaded, selecting an embargo period as established in the formal data policy. At the time of writing this report, the choice of public repository has not yet been finalized, but Zenodo is being strongly considered as a viable option.

The following Figures 4 – 6 illustrate the user interface developed for metadata input.

Figure 4: **General Information Tab.** This tab allows users to enter proposal details, including the proposal code, abstract, principal investigator, and experimental team information.

Figure 5: **Experiment Setup Tab:** This tab includes the beam settings, such as element selection, energy, and charge state, as well as additional beam settings and geometric configuration.

ToF-ERDA Metadata Generator

General Info.Experiment SetupDetection System

3. Detection System

3.1 Time of Flight Detector

Sample-T1 distance [mm]:

Length of flight [mm]: Polarity BIAS [V]:

3.2 Time of Flight Detector Electronics

Shaping time (μ s):

Amplifier Coarse Gain: Amplifier Fine Gain:

ATC Gain: ATC Range:

3.3 Energy Detector

Sample-Detector distance [mm]: Polarity BIAS [V]:

3.4 Energy Detector Electronics

Shaping time (μ s):

Amplifier Coarse Gain: Amplifier Fine Gain:

ADC Gain: ADC Range:

3.5 Common Electronics

Coincidence window [ps]:

Save Detector

Save JSONLoad JSONClean JSON

Figure 6: **Detection System Tab:** This tab provides input fields for configuring the detection system, including time-of-flight and energy detector settings

4. Conclusion

The adoption of FAIR principles in the nanoscience research infrastructure community is a strategic issue for ensuring the sustainability, reusability, and interoperability of scientific data. This document, which draws on lessons learned from the ExPaNDS and PaNOSC projects, offers a coherent set of recommendations, tools, and best practices to support both large and small infrastructures in this transition.

By emphasizing clear data policies, robust metadata structures, the use of persistent identifiers, and integration into ecosystems such as EOSC, the RIANA project actively contributes to enhancing the visibility and impact of data produced by European facilities.

The concrete example of implementation in two medium-sized infrastructures (CMAM and CNA) demonstrates that a gradual, pragmatic, and collaborative approach can overcome resource constraints and technical complexity. This approach can serve as a replicable model for other similar facilities.

Finally, this guide is intended to be evolutionary: it provides a solid foundation on which infrastructures can build to refine their practices, strengthen their integration into the European FAIR ecosystem, and thus maximize the scientific value of their data.

References

- [1] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.1 Draft extended data policy framework for Photon and Neutron RIs (Sep 2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014811>
- [2] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.2 Draft recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron data management (Dec 2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312825>
- [3] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.3 Final data policy framework for Photon and Neutron RIs (Aug 2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5205825>
- [4] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.4 DMPs for Photon and Neutron RIs (Nov 2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5636096>
- [5] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.5 Advanced infrastructure for PIDs in Photon and Neutron RIs (Mar 2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5905351>
- [6] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.6 Self-evaluation Photon and Neutron RIs for FAIR data certification (Dec 2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7246802>
- [7] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.7 Final recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron data management (Jul 2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6821676>
- [8] ExPaNDS Deliverable D2.8 Active DMPs for Photon and Neutron RIs (Dec 2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7223438>
- [9] ExPaNDS Deliverable D3.2 ExPaNDS ontologies v1.0 (Jun 2021) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4806026>
- [10] ExPaNDS Deliverable D3.3 Demonstrate ICAT and SciCat released with APIs compatible with ExPaNDS federated EOSC services (Mar 2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363591>
- [11] PaNOSC Deliverable D2.2 DMP Template for facility users (Nov 2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5639428>
- [12] Research Data Alliance Recommendation FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines (Jun 2020). <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

Appendix: Draft of a Formal Data Policy for Small/Medium RI

This document describes the scientific data management policy that applies to the distributed ICTS IABA, composed by two different infrastructures, CNA (Centro Nacional de Aceleradores) and CMAM (Centro de Microanálisis de materiales). CNA is a mixed centre of the Universidad de Sevilla, the Junta de Andalucía and CSIC. CMAM is a centre of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. This data management policy will be implemented gradually, on a best effort basis, and according to available resources.

1. General principles

- 1.1 This policy on data management outlines the rights to access and ownership of the experimental raw data and metadata collected and/or maintained by CNA and CMAM.
- 1.2 Agreement with this policy is required for the allocation of public beam time.
- 1.3 Users are prohibited from accessing, exploiting, or distributing data or metadata as specified in this policy unless they have the proper authorization.
- 1.4 Intentional violations of the policy may result in the loss of access to data and metadata and exclusion from future proposal opportunities.
- 1.5 All data and metadata will be managed in compliance with Spanish Data Protection legislation (Ley Orgánica de Protección de Datos, LOPD).
- 1.6 The approval and modification of this document correspond to the government bodies of CNA and CMAM. The legal representative of CNA is the vice rector of research of the University of Seville (US). The legal representative of CMAM is the vice rector of research of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (UAM).

2. Definitions

Experiments performed at CNA or CMAM can be divided into several categories: public access (which includes regular user calls, friendly users, training experiments, in-house research, access through formal collaboration agreements, and contingency beam time managed by the facility), access obtained through specific partnership agreements, and proprietary access (which includes contracts with companies or particulars stating proprietary access).

This policy applies to experiments with public access and those conducted under specific partnership agreements. Experiments under proprietary access are conducted with confidentiality regarding the proposal, raw data, and results, and are therefore not included in this policy.

For the purposes of this policy:

- 2.1 The CNA and the CMAM are considered as two distinct facilities.
- 2.2 “Raw data” refers to the information obtained from experiments conducted using beamlines or other instruments at CNA or CMAM. This includes data produced either automatically or manually through facility-specific software or expert personnel to support the subsequent analysis of the experimental results, unless specified otherwise.
- 2.3 “Metadata” refers to the information related to the data collected from the instruments. This includes, but is not limited to, details about the experiment's context, the experimental team,

- the conditions under which the experiment was conducted, and other logistical aspects. The information provided in the experimental proposal will be part of the metadata.
- 2.4 The “Principal Investigator” (PI) is the person listed as the PI on the proposal of the experiment.
 - 2.5 The “experimental team” consists of the PI and any other individuals who are granted permission by the PI to access the resulting raw data and associated metadata.
 - 2.6 When the PI is not a researcher in CNA or CMAM, a “contact person” (CP) of these institutions will be designated, who will be a member of the “experimental team”.
 - 2.7 The “online catalogue” is a digital database of metadata that includes links to raw data files. It can be accessed through various methods, such as web-based browsers, among others.
 - 2.8 “Results” refers to the data, intellectual property, and findings produced from the analysis of raw data.
 - 2.9 “Open access” refers to content that is available to the general public, not protected by copyright or patents, and can be used by anyone. It implies unrestricted, but not anonymous, access at no cost. An identification procedure may be required, Data considered “Open Access” will be provided under the CC-BY license (Creative Commons BY, <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>).

3. Raw data and associated metadata

- 3.1 Access to raw data and associated metadata
 - 3.1.1 Raw data and metadata from public access or specific partnership agreements experiments, as described in section 2, will be made available to the public after an initial embargo period. During the embargo period, access will be restricted to the experimental team, led by the PI.
 - 3.1.2 US and UAM will provide custody of the raw data and associated metadata of CNA and CMAM, respectively, for at least 5 years after the embargo period.
- 3.2 Curation of raw data and associated metadata
 - 3.2.1 Raw data and metadata may be curated at CNA and CMAM facilities or elsewhere. When curated, the data will be organized in clearly defined formats, and CNA and CMAM will provide the necessary tools or methods for accessing the curated data.
 - 3.2.2 Raw data and metadata will be read-only for the duration of their life time.
 - 3.2.3 Each experiment conducted at the CNA or CMAM is expected to receive a unique persistent identifier. Anyone publishing results derived from open-access data must reference the corresponding identifier and any related publications, if available and necessary.
 - 3.2.4 High-level metadata from CNA or CMAM proposals, including Title, Authors, Abstract, and Beamline, will be publicly accessible once the experiment is completed. This information will be available on a specific experiment site on CNA or CMAM web pages, along with the persistent identifier and the subsequent publications.
- 3.3 Access to raw data and metadata
 - 3.3.1 Access to raw data and metadata after the embargo period will be facilitated via appropriate listing and search tools.
 - 3.3.2 Access to data will be limited to registered users. Retrieving data may involve accessing permanent storage, which could result in potential delays.

- 3.3.3 Access to raw data and associated metadata from CNA or CMAM experiments is limited to the experimental team for a period of 3 years (embargo period). Once this concludes, the data and metadata will be made publicly accessible. If a PI wishes to extend this period and keep their data private for a longer duration, they must submit a special request to the Director of the correspond infrastructure.
- 3.3.4 The PI, assisted by the CP, is responsible for ensuring that data is stored in the designated directories and that the experiment number is accurately recorded in the metadata for each raw data set. Failure to do so may result in the experimental team being unable to access the data or other users accidentally gaining access rights to it.
- 3.3.5 Authorized staff from CNA and CMAM have access to curated data and metadata for purposes related to facility operations. The staff will ensure the confidentiality of CAN or CMAM data during the embargo period.
- 3.3.6 The PI has the possibility to transfer parts of the totality of her/his rights during the embargo period to another registered person.
- 3.3.7 The PI has the possibility to create and distribute copies of the raw data.

4. Results

4.1 Ownership of results

- 4.1.1 The ownership of all results (intellectual property) derived from the analysis of raw data is governed by the contractual obligations of those conducting the analysis and the copyright agreements established at the time of publication.

4.2 Storage of results

- 4.2.1 The PI may request to have the results of the analysis stored at CNA and CMAM facilities. However, CNA or CMAM will not be responsible for ensuring that the necessary software for reading or manipulating the results obtained from the analysis of data is available.
- 4.2.2 The US or the UAM cannot be made liable in case of unavailability or loss of data, results or data analysis software.

4.3 Access to results

- 4.3.1 During the embargo period, access to the results of analysis performed on raw data and metadata is limited to the experimental team responsible for the analysis, unless the PI requests otherwise.
- 4.3.2 Authorized facility staff, such as instrument scientists and computing group members, have access to facility-curated data and metadata for operational purposes. CNA and CMAM will ensure the confidentiality of this data is maintained throughout the embargo period.

5. Good practice for data and metadata capture and usage

- 5.1 The experimental team is encouraged to make metadata as comprehensive as possible. This will improve their ability to search for, retrieve, and interpret their data in the future.
- 5.2 CNA and CMAM commit to making best efforts to provide tools for capturing metadata items that are not automatically recorded by instruments. This ensures the most comprehensive description of raw data is recorded.

- 5.3 Researchers intending to analyze openly accessible raw data and metadata should, whenever possible, reach out to the original PI to inform them and propose a collaboration if necessary. They must also acknowledge the data source, cite its unique identifier, and reference any related publications.
- 5.4 PIs and researchers conducting analyses on raw data and metadata are encouraged to utilize the available on-line tools to link their analysis results with the corresponding raw data and metadata. Additionally, they are encouraged to make these analysis results publicly accessible.

6. Publication information

- 6.1 Publications associated with data from experiments conducted at CNA or CMAM must include the persistent identifier of the experiment and the data in their citations.
- 6.2 References for publications stemming from experiments at the CNA or CMAM must be submitted to the experiment site on CNA or CMAM web pages, within six months of publication or upon any new beamtime application, whichever occurs earlier. Failure to comply may affect future proposal time allocations.